

THE ITALIAN HIGHWAY SYSTEM IN TROUBLE WITH COMPETITION AUTHORITY: A CASE STUDY

ABSTRACT

The Morandi Bridge collapse in Genoa led to a series of sanctions against Autostrade per l'Italia (ASPI). In 2020, the Italian Competition Authority also took the decision of addressing issues related to competition. This paper examines how the Italian highway system operates and uses this case study to provide a clearer understanding of the concept of monopoly. The analysis is based on regulatory measures and institutional reports.

INTRODUCTION

In Liguria, after the fall of the Morandi bridge, problems are uncountable: works on the way, accidents and consequently queues. On the top of that tariffs were full: no discount for the delay, not even for commuters, indeed every year they augmented prices. This terrible situation is still existing: people are exhausted and very angry with ASPI. This is the only country where this happens: in Germany highways are free and well kept, in Switzerland you just pay €40 per year and you can move freely: Italy is the second highway most expensive of Europe after France, but in France the structure is perfectly well kept. The subject is absolutely current, interesting and important: the Italian government recently also tried a takeover and we are seeing the results in these times. This is what all about I am going to discuss in my essay.

THE DECISION OF THE COMPETITION AND MARKET AUTHORITY

The Italian Competition Authority - in Italian, Autorità Garante della Concorrenza e del Mercato, AGCM - is the competition regulator in Italy. It is an Italian quasi-autonomous non-governmental organization established on the basis of Law №287 of 10 October 1990. Since 2004, the Italian Competition Authority has also been in charge of enforcing laws against conflicts of interest for Holders of Public Office. As the Italian competition regulator, the Authority has the task of enforcing both Italian and European consumer protection laws. It is financed by annual allocations through a special chapter of the Ministry of Economic Development's budget.

The main duties of the authority are: vigilance against abuses from market dominance, against cartels (Anti-competitive practices), on takeovers; consumer protection, against unfair trade

practices and false advertising and finally supervise and penalize the cases of conflict of interest regarding members of Government of Italy. The measures and decisions of the authority are regularly published on its website.

The decision about ASPI, which include a set sanctions, is very recent it was published the last month and it is the result of proceeding started last July, because, even if sanctioned the company did not started any measure to reduce chargins. Immediately after the proceeding starting, the company offered a plan for a progressive reimbursement, called Cashback. With this decision of the Authority the plan was changed and now it is possible to obtain repaiment between 25 and 100% according to the mileage range and deley built up for work sites.

WHAT IS ASPI?

ASPI means “Autostrade per L'Italia” - in english – Italian Highways and is one of Europe's leading concessionaries for the construction and management of toll motorways, with around 3,000 km of network managed in Italy. The Autostrade per l'Italia group includes five other motorway concession companies and seven companies that provide complementary services to the core motorway business and play a key role in implementing the Company's transformation plan. The motorway concession companies in the Autostrade per l'Italia Group are:

- Società Italiana per Azioni per il Traforo del Monte Bianco operator of the Italian part of the tunnel for a lenght of 5.8 km;
- Raccordo Autostradale Valle d'Aosta a link road between Aosta and Mont Blanc for a lenght of 32.4 km;
- Tangenziale di Napoli serving the Neapolitan metropolitan area for a lenght of 20.2 km;
- Autostrade Meridionali which manages the Naples-Pompeii-Salerno motorway for a lenght of 51.6 km;
- Società Autostrada Tirrenica managing the Livorno-Rosignano-San Pietro in Palazzi section and the Civitavecchia-Tarquinia section for a total of 54.8 km.

Other Companies of the Group are:

- Movyon, which operates in the areas of research and development and integration of hardware and software systems in the field of Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS);
- Tecne, which coordinates the design, construction management and monitoring of the maintenance and investment plan, in partnership with Movyon;
- Amplia which is involved in the construction, maintenance and modernisation of roads and the development of road paving materials and technologies;

- Free-to-Xperience which deals with innovative services related to sustainable mobility and environmental sustainability;
- AdMoving which markets advertising space and services and manages events in service areas;
- Essediesse Società di Servizi which manages the administrative, general and real estate services for the whole Group and the debt collection and toll billing activities;
- Giove Clear which carries out cleaning activities on external yards, green areas and toilets in about 70% of the Service Areas of the ASPI network.

In 1950 IRI established the Società Autostrade Concessioni e Costruzioni Spa with the aim of participating, together with other major industrial groups, in the post-war reconstruction of Italy. In 1956 a first assignment between ANAS and Autostrade per l'Italia was signed and 1964 the Autostrada del Sole between Naples and Milan was opened. In 1982 Autostrade group was established. Today ASPI is a joint-stock company, operating in a natural monopoly, where the social costs of having more than one supplier are very high. In these market the demand of elasticities are very low and prices can be high. In these situations, some form of regulation may be necessary. In Italy we decide to offer highways in concession to a private organization since 1999. After the fallen of the Morandi's bridge, the government, temporally tried to come back to the state management: this controversy concerns all the Italian natural monopoly, such as water supply, electricity, telephone landlines, cable and airports. Until the spring 2021, it will be constituted a new company to which Atlantia Will transfer the 70% of his actions taken on the equity of Aspi. The public bank Cassa Depositi e Prestiti will pay an initial capital increase of four billions euros to cover Aspi's long-term debts and other 2 billions to buy the residual quote of 18% held by Atlantia in Aspi. As of September 2020, Atlantia owns the 88% of the equity of Aspi, while Edizione, an holding that owns the 30% of Atlantia. Autostrade per l'Italia as a whole is valued at 11 billion euros. In the following years, the Italian public property will have to finance extraordinary maintenance costs estimated of around 13 billion euros. In conclusion the point is that there is not so big different between private and public management, because we are talking about a natural monopoly. A strategy could be opening the market to new competitors, for example UnipolSai has just presented a device in competition with Telepass, and the European Union asked it with the Directive 520/2019, trasposed in the Italian system in 2021, but the obstacles are a lot and the new public management does not help.

MONOPOLY AND NATURAL MONOPOLY

A monopoly is a market with the absence of competition, creating a situation where a single firm is the only supplier of a particular output. Monopolies are characterized by a lack of economic competition to produce the good or service, a lack of valid substitute goods, and the possibility of a high monopoly price well above the seller's marginal cost that leads to a high monopoly profit. In other words monopoly is the right opposite of perfect competition. The verb monopolise or monopolize refers to the process by which a company gains the ability to raise prices or exclude competitors. In economics, a monopoly include a single seller. In law, a monopoly is a business entity that has significant market power, that is, the power to charge too high prices, which is associated with a decrease in social surplus. Monopolies can be established by a government, form naturally, or form by integration. In many jurisdictions, competition laws restrict monopolies due to government concerns over potential adverse effects. Holding a dominant position or a monopoly in a market is often not illegal in itself, however certain categories of behavior can be considered abusive and for this reasons it can suffer legal sanctions when business is dominant. A government-granted monopoly or legal monopoly, by contrast, is sanctioned by the state, often to provide an incentive to invest in a risky business or enrich a domestic interest group. Patents, copyrights, and trademarks are sometimes used as examples of government-granted monopolies. The government may also reserve the business for itself, forming a government monopoly, for example with a state-owned company. Monopolies may be naturally occurring due to limited competition because the industry puts a lot of resources and requires substantial costs to operate. Market structure is determined by two factors: barriers to entry and product substitutability. A monopoly is a structure in which a single supplier produces and sells a given product or service. In general, the main results from this theory compare the price-fixing methods across market structures, analyze the effect of a certain structure on welfare, and vary technological or demand assumptions in order to evaluate the consequences for an abstract model of society. More specifically a natural monopoly is an organization that experiences increasing returns to scale over the relevant range of output and relatively high fixed costs. A natural monopoly occurs where the average cost of production declines throughout the relevant range of product demand. The relevant range of product demand is where the average cost curve is below the demand curve. When this situation occurs, it is always more efficient for one large company to supply the market than multiple smaller companies; in fact, absent government intervention in such markets, will naturally evolve into a monopoly. Regulation of natural monopolies is problematic. The most frequently used methods dealing with natural monopolies are government regulations and public ownership. Government regulation generally consists of regulatory commissions charged with the principal duty of setting prices.

CONCLUSION

My essay considers the decision of the Authority about ASPI. First of all I analyze the decision about ASPI and in what consist the offer of INSPI to repay damaged people and firms. Than I analized the society of ASPI, his history, his structure and the market where it operate. I was hired as an economic consultant by a transportation company owner, which is very angry with ASPI: I exposed his point of view, his reasons and his working situation and I also made a comparison with the highway in the European Union's countries. Finally I analyze the structure of natural monopoly and its consequences for the market. In conclusion I have to say that the decision is very new and we don't see the effect yet: in the press release there is also a indication of a future advertising campaign, not realized yet, we will see if the plan "Cashback" will be sufficient to calm things down after the fall of the Morandi's bridge, covid and the last disastrous two years for italian highways, but for the ligurian in particular.

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